

A Secure and Privacy-Preserving Identity Framework

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Abstract— This paper proposes the idea of a privacy driven identity system and framework to securely authenticate and authorize citizens in various public services without exposing the sensitive personal information. Unlike various traditional identity systems, where users have their personal information printed on their identity cards printed, the proposed system displays on ID the random names and an alphanumeric code that links to the original identity details of the actual user that can only be authorized by secure backend mechanisms. Multi-factor authentication would be used to ensure that the ID used at public services is used by authentic user without showing in front of anyone. A secure portal would allow users to track where their IDs were used and make changes if needed. This design ensures minimum user data exposure to any breaches and improves privacy posture at various public services so that staff cannot use the user data for any malicious intent. This model also ensures the privacy protection and reduces the repetitive form filling at public service points. Challenges such as system integration, scalability, and legal compliance are discussed alongside potential applications in healthcare, transportation, and government services. The proposed framework offers a promising direction for balancing usability, security, and privacy in identity management.

Keywords— privacy-preserving identity; masked ID; secure citizen services; anonymous authentication; MFA

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, people's personal data is now increasingly under more threat of being exposed by various data breaches and malicious uses. Traditional identity systems displays people's personal information on their physical ID such as Full Names, address, contact information which can be exploited by malicious actors for identity theft, profiling and data misuse. Additionally if that data is stored in unsecure systems which are easy to breach, this can leads to data misuse, selling and other malicious purposes.

To address this issue, this paper proposes a Secure and Privacy-Preserving Identity Framework to authenticate, authorize and keep the sensitive information confidential of people at various public services. The core idea is to use an ID system where the personal data of the user is not shown and it is replaced with an alphanumeric ID string and random name linked to user's actual data. The physical ID would be NFC enabled and it can be used at various public services to authenticate and authorize users to avail services they need like eg: railway, bus, hospital. In addition with the physical ID, users need to provide biometric authentication or Mobile based OTP to verify that the person holding the ID is the same person.

This framework ensures that various public services like hospitals, public transports and other government offices can authenticate and authorize users without accessing or storing the personal data directly. Additionally users don't have to repetitively write all their information. The users have the facility of a portal to check where and how their IDs were used to facilitate accountability, audit trail and for legal purposes if needed. Users can also edit their information if needed through this portal.

The employees at public services are the second base of users who are going to use this facility. Every employee at public service that are using this framework must login in using their secure credentials to ensure that only legit employees are granted access to work. Each session of the employee is tied to employee's ID, time and the operation performed. This would be recorded in user's portal who used the service, allowing full transparency. To reduce the risk of unauthorized access due to negligence, the system automatically logs out after short period of inactivity.

Law enforcement agencies are the third base of users, the type of users that have the ability to access the suspected user's data by entering the alphanumeric ID string if they have any outstanding warrant or summons. Additionally to access the information, permitted and validated officers must have to provide their biometric data to verify in order to access the raw information of user to maintain the record of accessing the user data and no illegitimate person can view data. Every access to private information would be noted in user's portal as an evidence if needed for legal work. This ensures accountability, minimizing misuse and increasing the trust. Law enforcement officers also have the ability to red flag any user and it's associated ID if they have any criminal record. If that user or ID is used at any public service, the system would show red flag to public service employee and they may take appropriate steps to involve law enforcement agencies.

This paper explores the system's design, privacy benefits, security challenges, potential use cases, and implications for large-scale implementation in a digital governance context.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN AND PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The system design and framework consists of multiple components that are interconnected and working together to ensure secure, anonymous and verifiable identification of people across various public services that use this framework.

A. Random Name

A random name is a system pseudonym generated which is used to conceal the real name of user and it can be used by the system to process the queries. Random name cannot be same as real name.

B. Alphanumeric Identity String (Token)

A unique 12 digit alphanumeric string assigned to only one user which to links all the user data at back. It acts like a primary to all user data. The alphanumeric ID cannot be reverse engineered to get real user data as it hashed securely.

The formula to generate the Alphanumeric ID string (token) is

$$\text{ASID} = \text{First 12 digits}(\text{Base62}(\text{SHA512}(\text{AUD} + \text{BHU} + \text{S})))$$

Here,

- ASID = Alphanumeric String ID
- AUD = All user data
- BHU = Biometric hash of user
- S = Salting data

When all these data is combined in this formula, the resulting string would be the alphanumeric string ID that would be provided to user for it's identity. The total number of possible Alphanumeric string IDs is 3.22 sextillion.

C. Zone number

The zone number to a user is provided accordingly where the user applied to create their ID. The zone number is much more of a needed field for internal query processing. Anywhere this framework is implemented, zones would be divided to ensure that users are divided among zones and it makes searching within databases much easy and faster for the system reducing the processing load.

For eg: NEPD-077, NEPD is means the particular database in which user's data is stored and 077 refers to the table in that database where the user's data is stored. The written zone number would not be the same name for database or table name. It is a mapped alias which can be only determined by system.

D. Physical Card Design and It's Features

The physical card for users would be a simple to understand card which is very easy to use by the users and public service employees. The purpose of physical cards is to provide users a way to authenticate and authorise themselves when availing any service like railways, bus, hospital, govt service etc.

The physical card would be NFC enabled so that the card data can be scanned at public service kiosks without the need to enter the data by typing if scanning available. The design of the cards is similar to the size of debit cards, sleek, portable to carry anywhere.

Figure 1: Physical card sample design

- Random Name : A pseudonym generated by the backend system during the creation of ID to mask the real name.
- NFC chip : Embedded into card for quick and secure authentication of users at public service kiosks. Also reduces the need to authenticate by manually entering the information into the system.
- Alphanumeric ID string : A unique, system generated identity token used for authentication and query routing. This alphanumeric ID is linked to real user data.
- Zone Number : It indicates where the user's ID was created. Helpful in behind the scenes of quick verification of user's data through databases and tables. It indicates the in which database and table the user's data is stored.
- Security Watermark / Hologram : Adds a physical authenticity which can be determined by appointed public service employees.

E. Database Design

The Database is the most important part of this framework as it stores all the users data, public service employee's data and law enforcement officer's data. There will be multiple databases that will be divided according to the different zones. These databases would contain different tables of different zone numbers. This makes very easy for backend systems to make queries in databases as they have to search in less data when the zone is known.

For eg : zone – NDEP-077 means there is a database named NDEP and it has a table named 077(not necessarily). This type of segmentation would reduce the searching and querying by backend systems more fast. It will also reduce the amount of processing power required by the systems.

Figure 2: Database hierarchical architecture

The DB servers must use a very secure data storage options like Hashicorp Vault or any other secure services that would protect the data everytime. All the data must be stored in encrypted format (AES-256 encryption) to maintain the data confidentiality and integrity. Each server contains microservices that deal with requests of authentication and ID

creation. Data must be encrypted at all times while at rest and while in transit.

The database must have 3 tables,

1. Table of User's data
2. Table of public service employees
3. Table of law enforcement officers who are granted to access the data for investigation.

The separation of user's data is done to ensure that it becomes easy to retrieve the records and improves the role based access control. The table structure should look like this for Normal Users :

Table I: USERS DATA TABLE

Field Name	Description
User_ID	Internal primary key for internal uses(never exposed)
Full name (first, middle, last name included)	Encrypted with AES-256
Father's name	Encrypted with AES-256
Mother's name	Encrypted with AES-256
D.O.B	Encrypted with standard format
Mobile number	Encrypted with AES-256
Permanent address	Encrypted with AES-256
Fingerprint data	Hashed data
Iris Scan data	Hashed data
Masked ID	SHA-512 hashed of above data and salting
Date of creation	Standard date format
Validity	Users need to re-issue their IDs by re-verification of details
User Status	To show whether the user doesn't have any outstanding warrants or summons.(Red flag/ Green Flag)

Similarly the table for public service employee's data must be designed like user's but with little tweaks to ensure that important data is not missed.

Table II: PUBLIC SERVICE EMPLOYEES DATA TABLE

Field Name	Description
Employee_ID	Primary key and unique identifier
Full name	AES-256 encrypted
Department	AES-256 encrypted
Email ID	AES-256 encrypted
password_hash	Bcrypt with salting

Biometric hash	Added layer of security in case password is leaked
Date of creation	Standard date format encrypted
Date of expiry	Standard date format encrypted
Zone	For internal use only to make searching and query faster.
Status	(Active/Terminated/Inactive)

The accounts of public service employees must have an expiry date with an alert generated to ensure that only active working employees must be using the framework. Active employees must renew their account status through their superiors.

Similarly for Law enforcement officers the table structure should look like :

Table III: LAW ENFORCEMENT OFFICER'S DATA TABLE

Field Name	Description
Officer_ID	Primary key and unique ID for officers
Full Name	AES-256 encrypted
Agency (police etc.)	AES-256 encrypted
Biometric hash	Hashed data for authentication
Hashed password	Bcrypt hashed
Working Hours	Working hours starting and ending
Date of creation	Standard date format encrypted
Date of expiry	Standard date format encrypted

The law enforcement officers must also have date of expiry and needs to be renewed after a certain period of time to ensure that only active and verified officers can access the data in raw form.

To maintain the audit trail and accountability for the users of where their ID was used, we can use technologies like Kafka + hash chains which are used for immutable logging. This will be secure way to store the access logs while making it easy for the systems to retrieve the data.

F. Infrastructure Design(Backend)

The backend is also a crucial part of framework where all the queries, requests etc would be processed and data from databases would be retrieved to pass on to frontend. A secure backend is a necessary as without a secure backend, it would breakdown on various threats and loss lots of data breach.

Various security measures and protocols would be required to be placed in backend to protect data and various services.

Figure 3: Backend Architecture

Here 1 is the firewall, 2 is the IDS/IPS, 3 is the reverse proxy and 4 is a load balancer. Here PS refers to processing server and DB refers to Database.

- **Firewall** : The firewall acts as the first layer of defense in the backend architecture. It filters incoming traffic based on predefined rules, allowing only trusted IP addresses and ports to proceed further into the system. Whitelisting methods are used to limit exposure to unverified traffic.
- **IDS/IPS** : Placed directly after the firewall, the IDS/IPS monitors incoming traffic patterns and detects anomalies or malicious activities. The IDS logs suspicious activities, while the IPS actively blocks them in real-time, preventing known attack vectors like DDoS or port scanning.
- **Reverse Proxy** : The reverse proxy masks the identity and structure of backend components. It routes user requests to the appropriate internal services while also handling HTTPS termination and caching. This ensures both performance optimization and additional security.
- **Load Balancer** : The load balancer ensures that user requests are evenly distributed across multiple query processing servers. It helps prevent server overload and ensures high availability and fault tolerance in case of service failure.
- **Processing servers** : These servers handle incoming queries, create new users, authenticate users, and route requests to the appropriate zone-based databases. Each server is stateless and scales horizontally. Queries are optimized based on the *zone ID* embedded in the user's physical ID (e.g., "NEPD-077").
- **Databases** : it stores the data of all users, public service employees and law enforcement employees.

G. Infrastructure design(Front-end)

The frontend would be designed to be according to different needs of different users. There would be 4 different frontend interfaces for Normal users who just want to access

their portal to know where did their ID was used or edit any information. The second interface is for public service employees who are going to use the framework to repeatedly to authenticate the users. The third interface is for law enforcement officers who are going to use the framework for getting the data of normal user in raw form. This interface would require the most security as data would be displayed in raw form. The fourth interface is for the employees who have the job to help create new IDs of new user.

1) Frontend interface for Normal users

The frontend interface for the normal users would be easy to use and highly secure to ensure that no malicious actors can manipulate to gain data. The interface includes the login page where the users have to enter the masked ID they have, the input fields would be validated and sanitized to ensure that no SQL injection or XSS attacks occur. The interface would use HTTPS with TLS 1.3. It also implements CSRF protection. An OTP would be generated on registered mobile number which is needed to be provided in order to authenticate and provide the access the portal. There should be a rate limit to ensure that no bruteforcing or DDoS attacks occur. Session management would be implemented with session expiration after few minutes of inactivity. The input data would be encrypted here only before sending to servers to request.

2) Frontend interface for Public service employees

The frontend interface for public service employees would differ from normal users. It will be integrated into different types of public services that are used(eg. Roadways, hospital etc.). The interface would be required to be connected with biometric authentication devices to verify the users when using the masked ID. Eg : A railway ticket booking system for public employee would have a website where the employee would select the seat, train, date etc normally like traditional websites. Once the website requires the details of user, it will redirect to the masked ID link where it will require the user's masked alphanumeric ID to be entered. Once entered the user would be required to provide the biometric authentication like fingerprint or Iris scan to verify the masked ID is the actual user. Upon verification, the website would autofill the required details for ticket and continue with other steps as traditional website.

3) Frontend interface for Law enforcement officers

The frontend interface for law enforcement officers would look very different. The officers would be required to connect via VPN or jumpserver (preferred one) to connect to the interface. The system would provide the way to input the masked alphanumeric ID, provide the biometric authentication to access the information. Once the authentication is complete, the output would be raw user data.

4) Frontend interface for User ID creation

The frontend interface for user creation supports the creation of new user which can be further used in framework. Special employees who are employed to create new users are going to give work as intermediary between systems and users. The new users are going to enter their details into the system, once the system accepts the information, biometric details would be required to complete the process.

H. Data in transit security

The data which is transferred from frontend interface to backend interface for data processing and vice versa must be encrypted with secure encryption protocols like AES-256 or

better and TLS should be used in between to prevent any attacks like MITM.

Figure 4: Overall architecture of framework

I. Physical Enrollment and updating centers

A physical enrollment and updating center serves as the backbone of proposed framework for user's onboarding and data maintainance system. Users can apply to create their new IDs and update existing IDs as well. The centers are located everywhere in a calculated manner to ensure accessibility to everyone. The center should also operate under strict compliances of data security, integrity, confidentiality and privacy to protect user data. The main functions of the centers is to

- enroll new users into the framework
- update the details of user in it's ID when needed (with re-verification)
- reissuing of physical cards in case of loss, damage and expiry
- biometric re-verification

J. Backend Microservices functions

There will be various microservices that are going to be used to perform various tasks behind the scenes to ensure that there is no steep learning and difficulty in understanding by different users. Neither the developers and maintainers nor the actual users can't see the all data stored in raw form.

1) Physical ID Creation Process

To access the services through proposed framework, individuals are required to obtain a physical ID. This process is done at authorized physical enrollment centers that ensure security and confidentiality of data.

Applicants first fill out their personal information using an Optical Mark Recognition(OMR) sheets, which are directly scanned by computer systems and no human intervention is required during this step. This step ensures that staff cannot misuse or retain data during processing.

Once this step is completed, the staff of physical center would guide users through biometric registration, which includes iris scan and fingerprint scans. The users have to now provide birth certificate, address proof to prove their date of birth and place of living. If the information is not matching between application and proofs then the process is stopped there only. Once all the data is collected and sent for processing at server, the OMR sheet is destroyed to prevent authorized storage and retrieval.

The information sent at backend is now processed appropriately, so that it can be stored in databases. The information is first checked in servers for any duplicacy, if the information is duplicate(expect Address as it can be same for some users), the process is stopped and user is notified to provide the correct details. If all necessary details are correct, a mobile based OTP is generated to verify the phone number. Upon providing the OTP to the system by the users, the backend will store the data in User's database according to the Zone in which user applied for the ID securely using appropriate security protocols and measures. Using the personal information, an Alphanumeric string ID is generated for the user and checked whether the ID is unique or not. At the same time, a random name is also generated for the user and zone is mentioned in the user's ID. Once this is done, a request to create the ID in physical form would be submitted by the system. The user can collect their physical ID from authorized enrollment center. For eg : A user visits the physical enrollment centers to apply for new ID. He fills out an OMR sheet with his details. After filling the OMR sheet, it is submitted to computer for scanning and getting data from OMR sheet. Once the data is entered into the systems, checked for duplicacy, the user would be prompted to provide biometric details with the help of an enrollment center employee. Once this is done, user would recieve a mobile based OTP to provide to complete the process of issuing new ID. The user would be given a date of pickup, when he can collect his physical ID in a concealed form from the enrollment center.

The user IDs would have a validity for some years and after that users need to re-issue their IDs with re-verification to ensure that all the details are upto date. For eg: if a child was issued an ID before the age of 16, they must reverify their details and provide new biometric details to make their ID up to date.

Algorithm 1 : Physical ID Creation Process

1. START
2. User visits the physical enrollement center
3. User fills the OMR sheet to provide basic information
4. User provides birth certificate and address proof
5. If the documents don't match with provided OMR information, goto step 6 else if the information matches, then go to step 7
6. Notify user to provide correct details and verify once again.
7. Once the information is verified, collect biometric data
8. Once the biometric collection is complete, check the data in system for duplicacy. If data is duplicate then goto step 9 else goto step 10.
9. Terminate the application to provide the correct details.
10. If the details are not duplicate, generate a mobile based OTP to verify the mobile number
11. If OTP is not verified, goto step 12 else goto step 13
12. Terminate the application form
13. Once the OTP is verified, create alphanumeric string ID using provided user data.

14. Use the alphanumeric string ID creation formula.
ASID = First 12 digits(Base62(SHA512(AUD + BHU + S)))
15. If the created ID exists in the database already, goto step 16 else goto step 17
16. Regenerate the ID until it is unique
17. If the ID generated is unique and it is not associated to any user, use it, assign zone to the user and generate a random name for user's details.
18. Store all the necessary details in User's database and table according to the zone where the user submitted to create the ID.
19. Trigger physical card printing
20. Notify user for Physical ID collection
21. END

2) User Authentication and Verification Process

This is an important function that would be integrated into various public services like hospitals, railway station or government offices- to avail the service or to enter a restricted area, they must present their physical ID for authentication. To authenticate and verify users to ensure that only right users are getting the services they availed. The public service employee scans the NFC-enabled ID, which retrieves the user's alphanumeric ID string on the employee's system. To verify the identity of the cardholder, the user is then required to provide biometric authentication via a fingerprint scanner or iris recognition device. This step ensures that the individual presenting the ID is actually the rightful owner.

Simultaneously, the system checks the user's ID against any red flags set by law enforcement agencies. If no red flags are found and biometric verification is successful, the user is authorized to proceed with the requested service.

A detailed log would be created each time when a physical ID is used within the framework. The details include like Time, Date, Place where it is used, Employee ID, type of operation performed. Even if the any ID fails the biometric authentication, a log would be still created to notify the users about the attempt. This ensures transparency and allows users to be notified of any activity involving their ID's activity, whether successful or not. And for the public services to store the data, they would only store alphanumeric ID, zone and random name of user only. This prevents excessive storage of PII and SPII data. Even if a breach occurs in public service's server, the data wouldn't be much useful or make any sense to the hackers. For eg : suppose a user needs to take train, user visits the railway ticket booking counter for ticket booking. The user tells the employee about the train number, date of travelling and other options of travel first. Once this is done, user is then prompted to provide the details alphanumeric string ID, zone and random name. Then the user would be prompted to biometric verification to verify. Once the verification is successful then user would continue with ticket procedure like payment. Once all the processes is done, the ticket would be issued with only user's alphanumeric string ID, random name in the ticket and ticket ID that stores zone also if needed to check by the railway authority.

The employees at public service are marked with their status of working like active, inactive and terminated to ensure

that only authorized workers are working on systems for the time they have been scheduled.

Algorithm 2 : User Authentication and Verification

1. START
2. User arrives at public service kiosk
3. Kiosk employee scans the Physical ID of user to get Alphanumeric string ID
4. Prompt user for biometric authentication(fingerprint or iris scan)
5. if biometric verification fails goto step 6 else goto step 7
6. terminate the process and notify the user, log the activity of unsuccessful attempt
7. check for red flags by law enforcement authorities on User's ID.
8. If found any goto step 9 else goto step 10
9. Notify kiosk employee and law enforcement to take appropriate action necessary
10. No flags found, grant the access to the user
11. Log the session with time, date, place where it is used, employee ID, type of operation
12. END

3) Law Enforcement Officer's Access control

The law enforcement officers are given special rights to access the information in raw form according to the proposed framework. Specially designated officers would be authorized for this access. To access the framework, authorized law enforcement officers need to login using their secure login credentials and provide biometric verification for additional security.

If there is an ongoing investigation where the user data is required, officers can enter the user's any data available to them like alphanumeric string ID, zone, random name, even the real ID like Real name, Address, phone number and email ID accordingly what is present to search. Search can be made with only one point of data also, but it will take more time to search from database. when more details are provided, the search within the database can be done faster. Once the data of suspected user is entered, the investigating officer who is authorized to use the system, must now do biometric verification to make sure that only authorized users are using this system. If the verification is successful, the officer would be granted with the user's full details like Full name, Address, Phone number, email ID and the logs of the user to know where were the last places his ID was used.

There will be an option given to the officer to red flag the user if they want to trace the user continuously. Every instance of data access of user's information, a log is also created for user that his ID's details were accessed by law enforcement. For eg : A user has outstanding warrant and is on the run. The police only know his real name and address with which user enrolled in framework. The police would login into the system, enter the name and address of the user. Once they enter the details, they would be prompted to provide biometric verification. Once everything is correct, the framework would search the database and provide the exact details of user with logs that tell where the user used his ID. Now police have the

option to red flag the user, he is needed to be arrested. Once his ID is red flagged, he is on tracking. Whenever and where ever he uses his ID, a red notice would pop on screen to alert the public service employee and prompted to call the law enforcement.

To maintain strict control over data access, the authorizations granted to law enforcement officers under this framework are temporary. All access privileges are automatically revoked every six months as part of a Privileged Access Management (PAM) validation cycle. This ensures that only officers currently in active service and with ongoing investigative roles are permitted to access sensitive user data. Reauthorization requires formal approval and identity verification to restore access, reducing the risk of misuse by former or unauthorized personnel.

Algorithm 3 : Law Enforcement Officer's Access to Data

1. START
2. Law enforcement officer tries to logs into system.
3. If the provided details of login credentials are wrong, goto step 4 else goto step 5
4. display message try again, if it is more than 3 times, make a cooldown for that system IP.
5. Once the provided login credentials are correct, prompt the officer to biometric authentication.
6. If there is a failure in biometric authentication, goto step 7 else goto step 8
7. terminate the login session and try again.
8. Check officer's working hours from database
9. If the login attempt is beyond working hours, goto step 10 else goto step 11
10. issue a notice to cease from accessing the framework beyond the working hours. Note the strike in database, if it is the 3rd strike, revoke the permission for that officer.
11. Direct from login screen to dashboard to access information.
12. Enter the known details of user, any which is present at the time of investigation.
13. Upon clicking for search, officer would be prompted for biometric verification. If the biometric verification fails, goto step 14 else goto step 15
14. Terminate the searching process.
15. Request the backend to search the required data and show all data that is matching provided search input data.
16. Create a log for the user whose data is accessed by law enforcement to record in his dashboard data.
17. Does user need to be red flagged. If yes then goto step 18 else goto step 19
18. red flag the user, record is updated in user's table data.
19. END

4) Red Flagging User and Alert Mechanism

The Red flagging and alert mechanism is a special tracking system which is a part of proposed framework to prevent users with criminal records from using the public services. Law enforcement agencies can red flag a user and it's associated ID if he has an outstanding warrant or summons or serious concern in their name. Once the red flag is done, it will be updated in user's table database. If that user attempts to use any public service, the public service employee would be notified about their red flag status and the employee can take required action to involve law enforcement agencies. This function must be used unbiasedly for all criminals and strictly for the purposes of democratic values only.

5) Form Auto fill

An additional feature provided for the users to reduce the efforts and reduce the time to fill a form repeatedly with same information everywhere. All the public services online portals that would be integrated with proposed framework. If the user opts for using this ID, the user must be prompted to enter the alphanumeric string ID, zone and random name. In addition, user must verify themselves via mobile based OTP if they are availing this service online themselves. Once they are verified, the user's alphanumeric ID can be stored on that public service portal if they needed to verify user's details. The user then does not have to fill the form details that are already stored by this framework. This reduces the manual errors and saves time of users. A log would be created about form autofill to ensure that user's know where their ID was used.

Algorithm 4 : Form Auto Fill

1. START
2. User is filling a form themselves
3. User opts for the proposed framework system for form auto fill
4. Login page appears to enter the alphanumeric string ID, zone and random name that user already has.
5. User is then sent a mobile based OTP to verify their authenticity. If the user fails in verification, goto step 6 else goto step 7
6. terminate the process and log the activity for user's portal
7. all the fields that are already present in framework's database like Full name, address, phone etc. Would be eliminated and only the user's Alphanumeric ID, zone and it's random name would be stored with the service his was trying to avail.
8. Log the acitivity for user's portal.
9. END

K. User Portal for accountability and dashboard

A user portal and dashboard is a service provided to users to monitor their ID card's activity and for legal purposes if needed. The portal for the proposed framework would show the details like date, time, location of the card where it was used, purpose of usage and employee ID of those employees who catered at public service kiosks. It also logs when law enforcements accessed your data.

To enter the portal, first users must need to enter their alphanumeric string ID, zone and random name. Upon entering the information, the user would be sent a mobile based OTP to verify the authentication. If the OTP entered is correct, users would be prompted to main site, where they can see various details of card associated with them. The dashboard would also let users edit basic information if there is a necessary change required.

L. Logging mechanisms

Logging mechanism is a method to store data of every event that is occurred while using this framework to ensure accountability and audit trail for everyone. Whenever an event occurs, while availing public service, law enforcement accessing the data, updating details, form autofill and user portal access.

M. Advantages of Framework

There are various advantages of adopting this framework.

1. Concealed Identity : Real identity is hidden using random names and alphanumeric string ID, protecting users from data breach, profiling, surveillance and misuse.
2. Zone based data storage : Information is distributed across zones for efficient querying, faster retrieval of data and local data governance.
3. Minimal human interaction : Use of OMR sheets and biometric systems reduce insider threats by limiting employee's access to sensitive information
4. Secure access for law enforcement : Only authorized officers with biometric verification and within working hours would be allowed to access user data if needed for investigation. This enhances accountability and auditability.
5. Red flag and alert mechanism : tracks the users who hold outstanding warrant, summons and can be threat to other people in society. It also allows proactive involvement of law enforcement.
6. Tamper resistant logs : every log is securely stored in backend to maintain accountability and audit trail for legal purposes if needed.
7. Always logging : for event is logged in system to ensure accountability and audit trail. Whether the usage was successful or unsuccessful, the event data would be stored.
8. Form autofill : Users can opt for form autofill service via proposed framework to reduce the time taken to fill forms repetitively.
9. Decentralized control via mesh network : to increase fault tolerance, resilience and security to the framework.
10. Always encryption : Data is always encrypted with highest standards of encryption to ensure that no one(except law enforcement) can read data without authorised permission. Even the developers and maintainers cannot read the data from databases.
11. Additional Verification : users are required to provide additional verification in the form of

biometric scan like fingerprint and iris if accessing the service at public service kiosk. If the users are availing the service online they would get mobile based OTP for verification.

12. Frequent PAM validation for Law enforcement : Permissions for officers would be revoked after every 6 months to maintain only active and trusted officers.
13. Unbiased use manadate : Framework explicitly supports democratic accountability by enforcing ethical use of red flagging and data access.

N. Limitations and Challenges of Framework

1. Infrastructure and Deployment Cost : Establishing physical centers, biometric devices, secure servers, and mesh networks nationwide requires significant financial and logistical investment.
2. Without Zone based search : If the zone number is not available (e.g., in investigations), search across multiple databases can cause performance bottlenecks.
3. Data breach and exploit risks : Despite encryption, a sophisticated cyberattack on centralized servers could still expose hashed or indirect identity data if not frequently patched and monitored.
4. Red Flag misuse : Risk of political or biased misuse of red flagging unless an independent oversight mechanism is enforced.
5. System misuse by insiders : While access is controlled, malicious insiders (e.g., law enforcement officers misusing access) remains a risk if PAM audits aren't strictly enforced.

O. Potential Applications of Framework

1. Public Service Access : Used at railway stations, hospitals, buses, or ration distribution centers to authenticate individuals securely without revealing sensitive data.
2. Law Enforcement and Investigation : Enables secure, traceable access to individual identity data by authorized officers, useful during investigations, surveillance, or missing person searches.
3. Border Control and Immigration : Can be used for identity checks at borders with quick verification, without exposing personal details unless required.
4. Welfare Distribution and Subsidy Systems : Prevents impersonation or fraud in government schemes like pensions, scholarships, food subsidies by verifying rightful beneficiaries.
5. Disaster Relief and Emergency Response : In natural disasters, the framework can help identify individuals quickly using physical ID and zone system, even without full internet access.
6. Secure Entry for Events and Institutions : Applied in campuses, examination centers, or public events for biometric-based entry while ensuring user data privacy.

7. Healthcare Access : Patient identity verification using ASID without revealing their entire medical history to public service employees.

III. EASE OF USE

The suggested framework is developed with simplicity to both the user and the authorized staff in mind. Users access the system mainly through physical ID card that holds no sensitive information in readable form, promoting privacy as well as easy handling.

Only physical ID and biometric input like a fingerprint or iris scan needs to be provided by users at the time of service. The authentication is rapid with no need for memorization of passwords or credentials.

Besides that, there is a separate user portal where people can track activity associated with their ID, check logs, request updates and edit limited information securely, with mobile based OTP authentication for entry.

Behind the scenes, government workers and police officers use the system through simple to use, role based protocols that guide them through access procedures with appropriate security screening and minimal training.

Semi automating most verification processes and using biometric authentication, the system delivers fast, efficient and good experiences without compromising on security or accountability.

IV. SECURITY AND PRIVACY CONSIDERATIONS

There are various security and privacy considerations that have been taken into thought while creating this framework.

1. Concealed identity Principle : The system guarantees that neither public service employee nor intermediary can view or access sensitive user information. Authentication and authorization are addressed through cryptographic proofs and biometric matches without exposing real user data in transactions.
2. Biometric Verification : Access and identity verification are tied to biometric verifications (e.g., fingerprint, iris scan) so that even if the physical ID is lost or stolen, it cannot be used.
3. Encrypted Data Transmission and Storage : Data is transferred securely (TLS) and stored in encrypted databases. Sensitive factors such as ASID and biometrics are salted and hashed prior to processing.
4. Multi-Factor Officer Authentication : There is access by law enforcers with credentials added to biometric authentication of the officer. All operations are tracked and audited.
5. Tamper-Proof Audit Logs : All activity—failed authentication attempts included—is logged irretrievably with timestamp, device/location, and employee ID. Users can see when and where their ID was accessed.
6. Red Flag Monitoring: Red-flagged users are tracked on all services, and alarms are immediately triggered at any point of access. Abuse of the function is avoided through officer accountability logs.

7. Data Minimization : The physical ID has no explicit personal data—only zone, random name, and ASID. This reduces the data surface exposed during in-person checks.
8. Privacy by Design : The system automatically imposes user anonymity in everyday use while still permitting the tracing of identity by law enforcement with appropriate clearance and logging.

V. DISCUSSION

The proposed framework is designed in such a way to provide privacy and secrecy to user's personal information while maintaining the accountability and availability at times needed. Unlike other systems where the user's ID has lots of personal details mentioned, which increases the chance of identity theft, impersonation by someone and profiling by public service employees. The proposed framework reduces these risks. Most other ID systems don't provide a portal to their users to see where their ID was used. The proposed framework also tries to eliminate the repetitive form filling at various public services as compared to traditional systems where user needs to fill the forms manually, which takes a lot of time and can have errors in it.

This framework can be integrated into various public services and private sectors can also integrate into their systems if needed. The system can be expanded into more sectors in future according to the needs. There are future scopes of improving and making changes to the system like upgrading to new encryption technologies, more secure technologies of IDS, firewall, DB and other services. Implementing this framework can be cost intensive and prone to errors if the hardware is low quality. The flagging and alert mechanism can become a notorious tool for activities that are against the democratic principles. So this function must be used with caution.

VI. FUTURE WORK

There are various scopes of improvement and upgradation that can be done in future according to the needs. This system can be incorporated into private sectors like banks, insurance companies etc. which can expand the use and makes it easy for its users to access more services. The more bigger the ecosystem, the more easy is for everyone to access any service they want.

In future, systems can/would be needed to more secure and newer encryption algorithms to enhance the security of data. This way the system would be protected to threats in a long run and advance sophisticated attacks. Newer technologies can be incorporated into systems to increase security and protect from various newer threats.

More provisions of accountability and audit trail can be included within the system to make stronger trust in public. Periodic review of compliance mechanisms could be automated to maintain high standards of privacy governance.

VII. CONCLUSION

The Secure and Privacy-Preserving Identity Framework offers a unique privacy preserving solution for the user identification authentication in both public and private services. By including zone based databases we can improve

the searching and querying within our databases to get faster results without putting a lot of processing servers. It empowers users with control over their identities while maintaining accountability through features like audit logs and red-flag mechanisms. The integration of law enforcement access, strict authorization protocols, and a user-facing portal adds multiple layers of trust, transparency, and usability. This framework has the potential to redefine digital identity management in a democratic and secure manner, laying the foundation for a more secure and privacy-focused future.

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